

Appendix B: Additional figures

In this section we show additional figures from the analysis. Figure 1 are the continuum maps obtained for each channel and band of the MIRI/MRS data, except the short and medium bands of ch1, as they presented many lines and emission or absorption features that prevented from selecting a featureless continuum region. We used these maps to estimate the PSF size, by measuring the FWHM of both nuclei. In general the PSF size is below $0.7''$ in all the wavelength range up to ch4.

We show in Fig. 2 the kinematic maps for the remaining ionised gas emission lines that are spatially resolved with the MRS mode of MIRI.

Fig. 1. Continuum maps for all the bands in each channel ordered from lower to higher wavelengths. The title of each panel indicates the wavelength range used (in rest-frame) to create the maps. The short and medium band of channel 1 are not shown, as the spectra are dominated by emission and absorption features, thus there is no sufficient featureless range to estimate the continuum.

Fig. 2. Same as Fig. 4 but for [Ar II], [Ar III], [S III], and [S IV] lines. These three latter emission lines have been re-binned with a 2×2 box (see Sect. 2.2)